

Utilization and Design of Information System Analysis and Design in various Case Studies

Muhammad Fauzan Syahputra, *Industrial Engineering Andalas University*

Abstract— The effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect that can determine the progress or decline of an organization. Information system is a man-made system consisting of components within the organization to be able to present information. A good information system can improve the performance of all activities within the company that are supported by accurate and more secure data, so that all activities can run more effectively. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect the management's performance in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system. Therefore, it is necessary to design an information system so that it can simplify the flow of information. The design of this information system goes through several stages starting with a survey on the company, problem identification, system analysis, model design and finally by designing an information system.

Index Terms—Effective, Efficient, System Analysis, Information System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Management information System can be defined as a collection of interacting information systems that are responsible for collecting and processing data to provide useful information for all levels of management in planning and control activities. In theory, a computer should not be used in a MIS, but in reality it's impossible for a complex MIS to function without involving the computer element. Furthermore, that MIS is always associated with information processing based on computers (computer-based information processing). MIS is a collection of information systems.

All of these information systems are intended to provide information to all levels of management, namely lower level management, middle level management and top level management. Top level management with executive management may consist of the president, director (vice-president) and other executives in marketing, purchasing, engineering, production, finance and accounting functions. An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information. Information system is one aspect needed by the organization. The progress or decline of an organization is represented by the effectiveness and efficiency of the information systems used by the organization. The general objectives of the information system include: (1)

Providing information that can assist the management decision-making process; (2) Facilitate the implementation of daily operations; and (3) Providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of management transparency. The application of providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization is promotion. This form of online marketing provides a great opportunity for companies to expand market segmentation without the limitations of space and time. Marketing activities carried out with the support of the internet, one of which is a mobile web service. The mobile web can be used by a company to support business activities such as presenting company information, marketing products or services, and making it easier for customers to find information about the company. Information systems must be able to support the company's business strategy. The business strategy is realized through a series of business processes, so that the ideal business process is the foundation for the development of information systems

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

The definition of an information system can be derived based on the definition of each of its constituent words, namely system and information. Anggraini and Zega define the system as a collection of several elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal. A similar definition is also given by Jogiyanto who describes the system as a network of interconnected work to carry out an activity or complete certain goals. Systems can be groups of people, machines, things or other types of entities. Meanwhile, information can be defined as the result of data processing that has a certain value or meaning. Based on the definitions of these two words, Leitch and Davis define an information system as a system that connects the needs of daily transaction processing, operations support, management activities and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and external purposes. An information system is the result of human design and consists of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information.

Data dictionary is a collection of data and fact information from an information system as needed. The data dictionary stores the user name, the types of access allowed, the data item and the name of the data item in the database to perform these checks. While the data dictionary can store the size and type of data items, data item constraints, and item names in data

integrity checks. Data Dictionary consists of various kinds, namely: aliases or pseudonyms, names of data flows that flow on the DFD, data flows from or to processes, explanations used to explain existing information, data forms whether in the form of files, print outs or reports. , data structures such as data flows consist of anything stored in the data dictionary, period and volume.

Database can be defined as a collection of data that is integrated, organized and stored in a way so that it can be retrieved easily. A similar explanation is also given by Vanny and Syahyuman who define a database as a collection of data that is processed computerized into an interconnected and organized information that can be obtained quickly and easily. The main function of a database is to provide information to its users. Databases in information systems are used as: (1) a place to store data and information; (2) Tools to process data and provide reports regarding stored data or information. The data contained in the database must be logically integrated. This logical integration is referred to as a concept in the database. In addition to being integrated, the database must also be able to define the storage location. Data and information are stored in tabular form and are related to each other. Entity Relationship Diagram or also called ER diagram is used in documenting user needs and in designing a logical database using ER or semantic objects according to company policy. ER contains a complete set of entities with a number of attributes and a number of relationship components. The symbol is divided into two symbols, namely: attributes, entities, relationships, and links. Attributes describe the purpose of the relationship or entity. Entity or entity is a set of real or unreal objects where the data is stored, usually an entity is called a noun. A relationship, usually named with a verb and is a relationship that exists between a set of entities. Link, is a liaison between entities with their relationships and attributes. Database design is a process that produces a detailed data model of the database, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how tables and columns interact with each other. Term database design can function as an application of the whole design process, not just the structure database, but also queries and forms that have functions as part of the overall database within a database management system.

A good database design should minimize data repetition and achieve data independence. Repetition of data is storing the same data in several different files. Data independence can be achieved by placing data specifications in tables and directories that are physically separate from the program. Program refers to the table used to access the data. Changes to the data structure are only made once, namely in the table. Some of the benefits that can be taken from the use of a flexible and integrated database include: (1) Data can be used simultaneously; (2) Minimize data repetition; (3) Improve data accuracy; (4) Support transaction processing; (5) Maintaining data integrity; (6) Improve data security; (7) Meet the various data needs of the organization; (8) Maintaining data standards.

The steps of database design are: (1). Determine the purpose of creating the database. (2). Collect and search for all required information, such as order number and product name. (3).

Divide the data that has been obtained into a table, then divide each information in the subject or large entity. (4). Convert each information into columns and decide which name information should be stored in the table. (5). Specify the primary key, select the primary key of each table. (6). Set the relationship between tables. (7). Complete the design and then analyze the design. (8). Set the normalization rules.

The early history of PHP is the approach of the Personal Home Page (personal site), in the past PHP was still in the form of a script that functions as a form data processor from a server-side web which has an open source nature, and has the name Form Interpreter (FI). PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) has a syntax similar to ASP, Java, C languages, Perl and has the advantage of easy-to-understand and specific functions. The advantages of PHP are: (a). PHP programming language does not require compilation or compiler in its use. (b). It has an open source nature. (c). Many PHP applications are free and ready to use like PrestaShop, WordPress, etc. (d). Can make the web dynamic. (e). PHP has a lot of support from various web servers, for example, Appache. (f). It's easy to develop PHP applications. (g). PHP has the advantage of being faster than Java and ASP. (h). MySQL is an application package with PHP. The disadvantages of PHP are: (a). PHP has security flaws. (b). PHP code can be read by everyone. (c). The cost of encoding is very expensive. MySQL as a database management system is used simultaneously with PHP applications so that the server application is more powerful and dynamic. MySQL's advantages are: (a). Portability or stable enough to run. (b). Localization or can detect errors on the client. (c). Connectivity can use UNIX, IP, NT. (d). MySQL can be used for free. (e). Reliable security because there is encryption of passwords, user access permissions, and hostnames. (f). Has a high speed in handling queries and can process a lot of SQL every second. (g). More flexible than other databases. (h). Can be used at the same time without any problems by multiple users. (i). Interface with all applications. Disadvantages of MySQL for Windows are: (a). The program can only run on windows. (b). Applications that are slightly susceptible to viruses. (c). Lack of support for connection to visual programming languages. (d). Unable to accommodate server performance that exceeds the maximum limit.

III. DISCUSSION

Based on the journal with the title Design of a Marketing Information System for Island Tourism Biduk Island Based on a Mobile Web, a needs analysis carried out for the island tourism business in the Pisang River, the priority problem is the absence of an effective product marketing facility so that the island tourism boat transportation service from the biguk fishermen in the Pisang River can be more widely known. Provide more effective product marketing through internet media to disseminate information about island tourism transportation services on Pisang Island so that it can be widely known and can provide economic benefits for the fishing community of Big Dipper on the Pisang River. Therefore it is necessary to design a marketing information system for island tourism in Sungai Pisang to attract interest and increase the

number of tourists. Data related to island tourism in Sungai Pisang is collected and stored in a database designed using MySQL. This database is used in the designed marketing information system. Furthermore, the marketing information system for island tourism in Sungai Pisang, Padang, West Sumatra is designed for Biduk fishermen in an effort to increase marketing. To access the marketing information system of Biduk Pulau Wisata, it can be opened in browsers such as Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome and Opera, by typing biduakayah.com in the browser.

Based on the journal entitled Design of Quality Control Information Systems at Process Laboratory IV PT X A preliminary study of the spreadsheet-based information system used at the Process Laboratory IV PT X shows that there are still several weaknesses such as: slow information flow rate, minimal level of information security, and potential for various forms of fraud. This research was conducted to design a more efficient information system through the application of web-based applications. The results of the design involve four actors with different levels of authority and access. These differences will improve information security, so that various forms of fraud involving data manipulation by other parties can be minimized. In addition, the design of the information system also eliminates the repetition of set point data input activities that are usually carried out by Operator 1. Elimination of these activities reduces the time required to carry out the entire process, thereby increasing system efficiency. In addition, the elimination of repetition also minimizes the potential for human errors and writing errors in the data input process. Based on this, it can be concluded that the design of information systems with web-based applications has been able to help improve efficiency and minimize the weaknesses of existing information systems at the Process IV Laboratory of PT at this time.

Based on the journal with the title Information System Design in the PTPN VI Warehouse Section of the Ophir Business Unit, the data that has been collected from the literature review and direct survey to the PTPN VI Warehouse section of the Ophir Pasaman Business Unit, then carried out an information system design which includes system model design, system database design and system application design. The system model design is carried out to improve the system to be more effective and efficient. By designing a system model, we can create and understand the overall condition of a surveyed area system and be able to make improvements. After identifying the system components, the next step is to design an optimal information system. The design of the proposed system needs to be done to get a better system. Data is expressed as a collection of table relations or relationships. A relation is a two-dimensional table of data that has names. The purpose of this system design is so that application users can easily obtain the required data.

Based on the journal entitled Improvement of Warehousing Management Through the Implementation of Warehousing Information Systems at CV. ABB Warehousing information system implemented in CV. ABB has succeeded quite effectively in suppressing the problems that have occurred in warehouse management so far. With the warehousing management information system in CV. ABB, warehouse management becomes more accountable and transparent

IV. CONCLUSION

With the information system, the problems that have been described in the previously discussed journals can be solved. With an information system, it can improve the accessibility of data that is presented in a timely and accurate manner for users, without requiring an information system intermediary. Ensuring the availability of quality and skills in critical use of information systems. Develop an effective planning process. Identify skill needs information system support. Determine the investment will be directed to the information system. Anticipating and understanding the economic consequences of information systems and new technologies, and Improve productivity in systems development and maintenance applications

REFERENCES

- [1] Elita Amrina et al., "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pemasaran Biduk Wisata Pulau Berbasis *Web Mobile*," *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*, Vol. 18, No. 2, pp. 142-152, October 2019, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v18.n2.p142-152.2019.
- [2] Berry Yulianda, Ratri Fradinda Wulan, "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pengendalian Kualitas pada Laboratorium Proses PT X," *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*, Vol. 17, No. 2, pp. 113-125, October. 2018, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v17.n2.p113-125.2018.
- [3] Hery Hamdi, Oktavia Patriani, "Perbaikan Pengelolaan Pergudangan Melalui Penerapan Sistem Informasi Pergudangan di CV. ABB," *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 10-24, Mei 2017, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v16.n1.p10-24.2017.
- [4] Yudo Purnomo, Nilda Tri Putri, dan Elita Amrina, "Perancangan Sistem Manajemen Mutu Terintegrasi di Baristand Industri Padang," *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp. 80-88, July. 2017, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v16.n2.p80-88.2017.
- [5] Dina Rahmayanti dan Ringgo Afrinando, "Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pada Bagian Gudang PT.PN VI Unit Usaha Ophir," *Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri*, Vol. 12, No. 2, pp. 420-426, October. 2013, DOI: 10.25077/josi.v16.n2.p80-88.2017.